

Analysis of palladium(II) in micro amounts by a kinetic method

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Manuscript received 25 November 2002, revised 23 February 2004, accepted 11 May 2004

Palladium(II) catalysed oxidation of mercury(I) by chromium(VI) in acid solution has been utilised to develop a kinetic method for the analysis of palladium(II) in the range of 0.02 to 1.40 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-3}$ by spectrophotometric technique. Interference of a few ions were studied.

The millimolar quantities of palladium(II) are determined gravimetrically as dimethylglyoximate or ni oximate^{1a}. Micro amounts of palladium(II) are found complexometrically using cyanonickelate(II)^{1b}. The latter is a titrimetric method but involves the use of potassium cyanide in the preparation of the cyanonickelate(II). Other methods for the analysis of micro amounts of palladium(II) are available², among them being its spectrophotometric estimation³ as the azide and 2,2'-dithiodianiline complex. Palladium is known to catalyse several reactions⁴ but such reactions so far have not formed the basis of any kinetic method of analysis.

The kinetic methods of analysis are receiving considerable interest, since they are highly sensitive, selective, reproducible and less expensive. A small quantity of palladium is known to catalyse⁵ the reaction between chromium(VI) and mercury(I). Such palladium catalysis may be the basis of a kinetic catalytic procedure for the estimation of palladium in the μg range. In the present study, we have utilised palladium(II) as the catalyst for the chromium(VI)-mercury(I) reaction to the analysis of palladium(II) in micro amounts.

Results and discussion

The palladium(II) catalyzed chromium(VI) oxidation of mercury(I) has been studied in detail and its mechanism has been discussed⁵. The reaction has stoichiometry of 1 : 3 with an apparent less than unit order in mercury(I) and a first order dependence on chromium(VI), palladium(II) and H^+ concentrations. No effect of initially added products was observed. It is well known⁶ that, in aqueous solution, chromium(VI) exists mainly in the form of an acid chromate ion, HCrO_4^- . The results suggest that mercury(I) reacts with palladium(II) to give a complex which then reacts with chromium(VI) in a rate determining step which is followed by further fast steps to give the products and palladium(II) being regenerated. The results can be shown as follows

(Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The evidence for complex formation was obtained from UV-vis spectrum and from the Michaelis-Menten plot and such complex formation between substrate and catalyst has also been observed in other studies⁷. The active species of oxidant, reductant and catalyst involved in the reaction are HCrO_4^- , $[\text{Hg}_2(\text{SO}_4)\text{HSO}_4]^-$ and PdCl^+ , respectively. Increase of ionic strength and decrease of dielectric constant caused a decrease in the rate of reaction.

The effect of ionic strength and dielectric constant on the rate of reaction supports the proposed mechanism (Scheme 1). The negative value of the entropy of activation ($\Delta S^\ddagger = -30 \pm 2 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicated that the complex is more ordered than the reactants. The oxidation presumably occurs by an inner-sphere mechanism⁸.

At constant acidity, the rate constant (k_{obs}) is a linear function of the concentration of the catalyst only (Table 1). In view of this fact, a kinetic method of measurement of palladium(II) concentration becomes available. For this purpose, a calibration curve of pseudo-first order constant (k_{obs}) versus concentration of palladium(II) can be constructed

Table 1. Effect of Pd^{II} concentration on the oxidation of Hg^I by Cr^{VI}[Cr^{VI}] = 2.0 × 10⁻⁴, [Hg^I] = 1.0 × 10⁻², [H₂SO₄] = 0.50, *t* = 1.60/mol dm⁻³

[Pd ^{II}] × 10 ⁶ mol dm ⁻³	<i>k</i> _{obs} × 10 ³ s ⁻¹	Absorbance (1 min)	Δ <i>x</i> (1 min)
0 (Uncatalyzed)	0.037	0.575	0
1	0.96	0.515	0.060
2	4.07	0.479	0.096
3	5.83	0.455	0.120
4	8.15	0.425	0.150
5	10.1	0.400	0.175
6	12.3	0.375	0.200
7	14.1	0.350	0.225
8	16.3	0.325	0.250
9	18.3	0.295	0.280
10	20.5	0.267	0.308
12	24.8	0.215	0.360
14	28.5	0.165	0.410
16	30.3	0.155	0.420
18	31.8	0.150	0.425
20	32.3	0.140	0.435

Error ±5%

from data of Table 1 under a known set of conditions of concentrations of oxidant, substrate, acid, temperature etc. The reaction is then repeated under similar conditions in presence of the solution of unknown palladium(II) concentration and the value of rate constant *k*_{obs} is used to get the concentration of palladium(II) from the calibration curve. Alternatively, under the conditions of the reaction, after a definite intervals of time, say 30, 60 s etc. one of the concentrations, that of chromium(VI) is measured both in the presence and absence of a known amount of catalyst. Such data again lead to a calibration curve and the unknown concentration of palladium(II) can be obtained from such a graph.

For routine measurements, the latter procedure is recommended. The rate constants and absorbances for uncatalysed and catalysed reactions are given in Table 1. Taking the difference in absorbance between catalyzed and uncatalyzed reactions as Δ*x*, a calibration curve of Δ*x* versus [Pd^{II}] is plotted. This plot is used for determining unknown concentration of palladium(II). The method enables analysis of palladium(II) in the range of 0.02 to 1.40 μg cm⁻³ of solution. However, for concentrations higher than 1.4 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³ of palladium(II) under the given conditions of the reaction of Table 1, deviations from linearity occur and the method is no longer satisfactory.

Interferences by a few metal ions were also tested for the palladium(II) analysis. Apart from the reductants which reduce chromium(VI) and the oxidants which oxidize mercury(I), it was found that Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cr^{III}, Zn^{II}, Mg^{II}, Sb^V, Ag^I and NO₃⁻ have no effect, where as Mn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Cl⁻ interfere. In all the cases, examined up to a concentration of 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ of the diverse ion.

The method finds its applications in the analysis of palladium(II) in micro amounts in its complex form (e.g. halide, thiocyanate, cyanide complexes of palladium(II) etc.), ores and minerals (e.g. platinum ore, sudbury ore etc.) and such other similar forms.

Experimental

A.R. grade chemicals and double-distilled water were used throughout. The chromium(VI) solution was prepared by dissolving K₂Cr₂O₇ in water. The mercury(I) solution was obtained by dissolving mercury(I) nitrate (Fluka) in HClO₄ (1.0 mol dm⁻³, 70%) and the solution was standardized against KIO₃ solution^{1c}. The palladium(II) solution was obtained by dissolving PdCl₂ (Johnson Matthey) in 0.20 mol dm⁻³ HCl and assaying for palladium(II) by complexometric titration with EDTA^{1b}. The chromium(III) solution was prepared by dissolving Cr₂(SO₄)₃, K₂SO₄·24H₂O (B.D.H.) in water. The mercury(II) solution was obtained by dissolving HgO (B.D.H.) in 0.50 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄. The ionic strength was kept constant using Na₂SO₄.

Kinetics were followed at 25 ± 0.1° and *I* = 1.60 mol dm⁻³. The reaction was initiated by mixing previously thermostatted reactant solutions, viz. chromium(VI) solution containing the required amounts of H₂SO₄, Na₂SO₄ and mercury(I) solutions containing palladium(II). The reaction was followed under pseudo-first order conditions, with mercury(I) concentration in excess, by measuring the absorbance of chromium(VI) in the mixture at 360 nm in a 1 cm cell placed in the thermostatted compartment of Hitachi 150-20 spectrophotometer. Validity of Beer's law under the reaction conditions had earlier been tested between 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ and 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ of chromium(VI) at 360 nm with ε as 1200 ± 12 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The pseudo-first order rate constants, *k*_{obs} were obtained from the plots of log (*a*-*x*) versus time. The pseudo-first order plots were linear over 80% completion of the reaction. Rate constants were reproducible within ±5%.

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